

Evidence-based methodology for identifying drugs with potential toxicities to the liver using US EPA ToxCast data set

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Research aim:

We seek to understand how the preclinical data generated in [US EPA ToxCast™](#) *in vitro* high-throughput program may be used to distinguish drugs that may be toxic to human liver versus those that are not (or have lesser degree of toxicity). For this investigation, we will evaluate drug pairs, wherein a drug withdrawn from the US market due to safety reasons (with or without a documented liver toxicity) will be compared to a drug that was still on the US market as of 1/1/2017, when the study was initiated. This project is part of a systematic review that is being conducted by EBTC with the registered protocol PROSPERO 2018 CRD42018112353(Tsaion, 2018).

Methods:

As an initial proof-of-concept, a single pair of drugs – Rosiglitazone Maleate and Troglitazone will be analyzed through the following steps. The choice of these drugs is based on their known role in liver toxicity and their classification as being “less DILI” for Rosiglitazone Maleate and “most DILI” for Troglitazone (withdrawn from the market in 2000). The US FDA’s [Liver Toxicity Knowledge Base](#) (LTKB) was used for DILI classification.

Hence, in this drug pair to be analyzed, there exists a drug that has been withdrawn from the US market due to most-DILI (based on US FDA LTKB) and one that remains remain on the market with less-DILI classification by LTKB, thus allowing us to determine if there is any difference between these drugs’ human safety profile and their preclinical data, in this case, a biological activity profile in the US EPA ToxCast™ *in vitro* tests.

Preclinical data sets of drug pairs will be retrieved from the publicly available [US EPA ToxCast™ database dashboard](#) – which represents the largest known, most curated collection of > 1100 molecular and cellular assays for up to 2000 chemicals including ~500 FDA approved drugs (Chen et al., 2016). The ToxCast data processing pipeline consists of multiple processing steps resulting in progressively refined estimates of AC₅₀ values from all the drug/test combinations (Filer et al., 2016). For this analysis, we will retrieve Level 5 (or the next step, Level 6) data containing AC₅₀ (activity concentration at 50% of maximal activity) values from the best performing model used to fit dose-response curves.

Assay Inclusion criteria: All assays in which drugs in scope were tested and which have a valid entry in the ToxCast database will be used in analysis.

Assay Exclusion criteria: All assays in which drugs in scope were not tested will be excluded for that drug pair.

As an initial step, all assays in which both drugs were tested and with a meaningful numerical response (i.e., AC₅₀ is not designated as 'NA' - for not available or AC₅₀ is not designated as '1000000' - 'dummy' variable for inactivity in an assay at all tested concentrations) will be retrieved. If the results warrant further analysis, as determined by the review team members, the following additional steps will be followed.

For further analysis, across all assays in which both drugs in scope were tested, their AC₅₀ values will be normalized to a normalized activation score (NAS) that reflects the difference between the peak concentration that a drug achieves in plasma after the drug has been administered to humans (C_{max}) and the AC₅₀ value for the assay in a cellular/*in vitro* model system. The human C_{max} used in this experiment with marketed drugs is taken from drug inserts.

The formula for the normalized activation score (NAS) is:

$$NAS = \frac{C_{max} - AC50}{C_{max}}$$

The NAS value will be used as a ranking metric to stratify assays/targets thereof in patients using the following logic:

- All assays/targets thereof with NAS value > 0 will be deemed to have a putative “higher activation potential”; this is because the C_{max} concentrations in patients are expected to exceed AC₅₀ values.
- All assays/targets thereof with NAS values < -4 but NAS > 0 will be deemed to have a putative “modest activation potential”. This is because the dose function in drug dose-assay response curves is represented using a log₁₀ scale implying at least modest activation of the assay/target thereof when NAS approaches -4 i.e., drug concentration is up to 5-fold lower than the AC₅₀ value.
- All assays/targets thereof with NAS values < -4 will be deemed to have a putative “low activation potential” given the greater than 5-fold lower concentration of the drug expected (based on its C_{max}) vs AC₅₀ value needed to activate the assay/target thereof.

All assays/targets and their pathways will be compared across the drug pair using NAS values either directly or after grouping them within their respective biological processes/target families or target sub-families represented within these assay descriptions in the ToxCast database. The goal of this comparative analysis is to identify those assays/targets/pathways that have higher activation potential in one drug compared to the other drug. A variety of visualizations will be used that highlight qualitative and quantitative differences between drugs being compared.

An outcome of the above comparative analysis will be the identification of differentially affected assays/targets/pathways for each of the drug pair studied. Biological targets that are associated with the tests will be identified using the ToxCast™ assay list of targets. Differentially affected targets will be highlighted visually and may be investigated further for their potential link with liver toxicity based on a literature analysis of their associated functions and/or a probabilistic analysis using a larger number of drugs classified by their known roles in liver toxicity as per US FDA's [Liver Toxicity Knowledge Base](#) and observing activation of similar assays/targets in these.

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